

Provision of a Model Claim Management in the DBB Contracts

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ABSTRACT: The increase in the claims in the construction industry is inversely correlated with the achievement of the three goals of project management (time, cost, and quality), as with the increase in the claims, the time and costs are increased, and the quality of the project is decreased. The traditional project delivery system (DBB) separates the role of participants in the design and construction stages and, in other words, restricts the cooperation of the construction contractor or manager in the design stage. Therefore, the current study aimed to provide a model to manage the claims in the DBB contracts. The research methodology is applied with a developmental approach. In terms of data collection, it is descriptive research with a design strategy. The statistical population included all the faculty members, professors, and managers in the construction field. The SPSS was used for the data analysis in the current study. Based on the findings, it was revealed that the lack of harmony between the payments and invoices, suspension from work, insufficient definition of the scope of work, orders of change in the project, unilateral termination of the contract, stoppage of work by the contractor, design defects, changes in excess of the contract, disagreements in evaluation, ambiguity in the contract, violations in construction, harsh weather conditions and slow work, not clearly defining the responsibility of each of the parties to the contract, not responding to each other on time, the cost of the project rising above the contractual limit, the irresponsibility of some agents, the lack of timely provision of financial resources by the employer for the contractor, lack of sufficient supervision by the employer on the project implementation process, unequal contract conditions and a imperious view of the contractor, engineers not being familiar with the features of construction contracts, etc. are influential in the emergence of claims.

Keywords: Model, claims prevention, DBB contracts

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1. Introduction

The construction industry is one of the main economic sections of Iran that plays an essential role in creating job opportunities and economic growth (Dastyar et al., 2018). It

can be said that a nation's progress, welfare, and excellence are highly dependent on the success of its civil projects (Chong et al., 2017; Seidoughi et al., 2016). The discussion of claims in civil projects is critical due to its impact on the project objectives. The claims are time-consuming and costly occurrences in the projects that have made problems for the country's civil projects (Ansari & Abbasnejad, 2018). The claim is defined as a request by one of the parties to the contract to modify some parts of it that lead to the payment of extra money, an increase in the project time, or other compensatory measures in terms of the sections of the contract. It has created many challenges for the projects and sometimes led to projects shutting down (Jaryan & Nasirzadeh, 2017). Claim management is among the most critical discussions and challenges the projects face worldwide, and many project beneficiaries consider it one of the most destructive incidents in the construction industry (Jaryan & Nasirzadeh, 2017). The increase in the claims in the construction industry is inversely correlated with the achievement of the three goals of project management (time, cost, and quality), as with the increase in the claims, the time and costs are increased, and the quality of the project is decreased (George et al., 2017). Although the possibility of claims cannot be eliminated in any project, it is possible to primarily prevent them from occurring in future projects by identifying the main causes of claims and the relationship between them (Bagherpour & Musavi, 2018). The main causes of lack of proper efficiency in the construction industry are the scattered nature of the project delivery, the use of traditional 2-D CAD technology, and the small size of most construction buildings. On the other hand, using the common and traditional method of two-dimensional CAD drawing does not create a cooperative approach. The architects and engineers prepare their CAD drawings and provide them to the owners and contractors. These drawings will not integrate into each other, and usually, in some parts of them, the drawings' information contradicts each other, which causes a lack of proper productivity (Jan 2018).

Also, construction projects are complex, unique, and dynamic due to many influencing factors, high financial circulation, specialization and uniqueness of activities, workload, novelty and innovation, sensitivity, diverse locations, and the involvement of different people in the project. Also, on the other hand, the construction industry is always facing problems that increase the time and costs of the project, and that is a reason why the project is not completed with the intended quality (Taghizadeh et al., 2015). The claims and conflicts may emerge in the contracting agreements due to different reasons (Salmani & Ghorbani, 2018). Such conditions increase the probability of claims and conflicts in different stages of project implementation (Bakhari, 2016). Sometimes, after the claim is raised, much time is spent to settle it, and sometimes, due to the passage of time and the problems becoming obsolete, some new aspects are added to the claims, becoming more complex. As a result, more cost is imposed on the project. Since the number of claims in the construction project is increasing, determination of their causes and clearly understanding the complexity of the factors causing a claim and their relationships are the main steps to prevent the claims and reduce them (Nicola & Augustin, 2018). One of the biggest problems currently the contractors are faced with is the impossibility of construction of the maps provided to them by the consultants in a way; that in many companies, it has become a standard procedure that contractors to produce plans called workshop plans (shop plans) in which the construction details are observed in such a precise way that the building can be built from them. It has always been time-consuming and costly, and sometimes it is the

source of disagreement between the consultant and the contractor. Therefore, knowing the causes of claims and disputes makes it possible to identify and adopt methods to prevent them from occurring, but what is currently being discussed about these contracts is a large volume of dispute cases and contractual claims in projects, and unfortunately, there is not a proper procedure done legally. Furthermore, there is no systematic way to handle and end this dispute (Seo and Kang, 2020). This is where the discussion of claims management is raised. The analysis is done by summarizing the critical field points and research estimates of technical and financial capacities based on the results of the project and the research literature (Farahani Hemmati M et al. 2022)

The complexity of the contractor's claim system in construction industry projects, especially in the turnkey contracts where the contractor faces more risks and has more responsibility, requires a detailed understanding of the existing claims (Zaneldin, 2018). Mainly, in international projects, and from the middle of the project onwards, it is necessary to identify all the elements of the project in order to fully understand the claims that have arisen and how they relate to each of the components of the project system, in order to prevent the occurrence of multiple claims. Also, with the management of the claims, the claims arisen should be dealt with in more detail. To do so, the system dynamics method must be necessarily used. (Parchami, 2017). Claims are also becoming inseparable parts of contracts, and by identifying these claims, their occurrence in the project can be prevented to a large extent (Parchami et al., 2014). Claims and subsequent disputes have become the inherent characteristics of the construction and production industry, which many project beneficiaries consider to be one of the most destructive events in this industry. Although the possibility of these claims cannot be eliminated in any project (Sultani et al., 2017), identifying the factors that cause it can be prevented to a large extent (Nadafian et al., 2015). Thus, the current study should answer the question: What model can be provided to manage the claims in the DBB (Design-Bid-Build) contracts?

2. Literature Review

Kanani (2018) dealt with the management of lawsuits and claims in the project from the perspective of private and urban construction. The purpose of this article was to learn how to prevent common problems in procurement and resolve disputes between the employer and the contractor, and as a result, reduce time and cost, increase the efficiency and profitability of the project, and achieve the desired benefits for the parties. In this regard, to reach a practical and step-by-step solution according to the requirements and time limit of the discussion, firstly, in the first part, the basic concepts will be introduced very briefly, and then in the second part, the existing challenges and their roots will be investigated. Next, and based on the first and second sections, in the third part, the requirements, steps, and processes necessary for the optimal management of contracts and contractors in the project and the reduction of lawsuits, claim, and disputes between the employer and the contractor will be discussed. Dana (2018), in research entitled "management of claims in projects, according to the existing standards," concluded that in recent years, the increase in construction has caused a large number of credits to be consumed annually in this sector, and on the other hand, it also faces problems. For various reasons, the parties may object to the laws. In public and private projects, this is possible.

Inflation, lack of liquidity, and other factors can be the causes. Amani et al. (2018), in research titled "Identification of the causes of claims in Iranian construction projects with the three-factor contracts approach," concluded that a significant part of the frequent causes in the base research is related to the employer. It was also found that some causes of the occurrence of claims in Iran differ from the results obtained from the analysis of the base research, according to the conditions governing the country's projects.

Parchami and Moradi (2018), in research titled "Claims Management Office, a solution for implementing claim management processes in the contractor-oriented construction industry," concluded that one of the biggest challenges in the construction industry is claim management in projects. Correct implementation of claim management processes is one of the ways to overcome these challenges. Nevertheless, there are many problems in implementing these processes in the project. One of the most important solutions obtained in this research is employing experts in the field of claims and using them in an institution called the Claims Management Office in the project. Bagherpour and Musavi (2017), in research entitled "providing an interpretive structural model for claim management in construction projects," have concluded that the four reasons as choosing a contractor with a lower price without considering technical competence and ability, low contract price due to competition above, ambiguity and contradiction in the documents or provisions of the contract, and sudden and unexpected changes in the exchange rate and bank interest have the highest influence and impact than other causes, and as a result, have the highest importance in reducing and preventing the occurrence of claims. Taheripour et al. (2017), in research entitled "Causes of Claims in Construction Plan Projects and Solutions to Reduce Them (Case Study: Civil-Subsurface Projects in Tehran)," concluded that the implementation of projects by the construction plan method in the country is a new, compared to the existing project implementation systems, and the parties to the agreement have little familiarity with it. For this reason, conflicts between these factors, especially in subsurface projects with a complex nature, will be inevitable. Salmani and Qorbani (2017), in research titled "claims management and identification of the main causes of claims in construction projects," concluded that among the most important issues and challenges that threaten the process of project implementation is the occurrence of claims in construction projects, which results in the cases like breaking the relations, parties' conflicts, and most importantly, delay in the project. In most projects, claims from the parties, especially contractors, are possible. These claims have negative effects on the implementation of projects. Although the possibility of these claims cannot be eliminated in any project, it is possible to prevent them from occurring in future projects to a large extent by identifying the main causes of claims. Parchami Jalal and Moharari (2020), in research entitled "providing a model for preparing optimal contracts to prevent claims in projects," identified the main reasons for the increase in claims in projects using the library research and document analysis methods. Then, by complementing and combining related models, adding a communication agent as a contributing factor, and providing a training bank of contractual knowledge, a new model can help prepare optimal contracts and thereby effectively either reduce or prevent claims.

Zhou et al. (2020), in research titled "simulation of construction project delivery system decision under sustainable construction project management," have concluded that

based on multi-agent systems (MAS), a decision simulation model was developed for project delivery system decision-making. When analyzing the conditions under which owners tend to choose DB or DBB, they reached the following conclusions by the use of the project delivery system decision-making: (1) the contractor's technology and capabilities increase faster in DB than in DBB; (2) The project delivery system with policy and market settings has the decisive advantage of the project delivery system, and the owners are more willing to choose the project delivery system that was previously chosen. (3) The mechanism of competition in the construction market will eliminate contractors whose growth rate is too low to meet the needs of projects in the market. Lee and Borman (2020), in research entitled "Building Information Modeling and Management," concluded that Building Information Modeling (BIM) could allow the client to match the designs offered by design companies and institutions with safety, fire extinguishing, lighting, energy topics and topic 11, and construction and coordination costs, and confirm or reject it. After this, the employer can conduct a correct and precise contract bid. Lindhard and Larsen (2020), in research titled "identifying the key factors affecting the construction project performance," have concluded that a construction project traditionally involves different participants. Owners, consultants, and contractors have different opinions and interests, but they all seek to ensure the project's success. Success is typically measured as cost, time, and quality performance output. The emergence of a claim in a construction project can significantly reduce the performance of the project and the speed of the project, so it is necessary to adopt claims management approaches. Mota et al. (2019), in research entitled "Building Information Modeling for Production: Advantages and Challenges for Application in DBB Projects," have concluded that the effective use of the BIM has a positive effect on the speed of DBB projects; therefore, a skilled professional with design and construction knowledge is needed for the BIM. Hemmati Farahani M ,et al. (2023) Policymakers are the other governing stakeholders who empower all stakeholders on system applications. It was observed that the role of policymakers is significant to strength the other stakeholders and expansion. Rastegari et al. (2019), in research entitled "A model to determine the optimal strategy for resolving claims in construction projects," concluded that this model includes the strategies of the contractor and the owner in a four-stage process including negotiation, mediation, arbitration, and disputes. This helps the involved parties to have a deeper understanding of the problem, have a better assessment of their situation, and to analyze possible strategies in facing such a situation. Farahani, Mehrab Hemmati, et al. (2024),The purpose of this article is to increase the understanding of how design companies understand the benefits of using building information modeling technologies. Building information modeling has been recognized in the literature as a (potential) powerful driver that moves the construction sector towards sustainability. However, for design firms, the choice to invest in building information modeling technologies is primarily an economic one. By considering different scenarios, points that both parties can reasonably agree on are presented with an analytical solution. Finally, two cases of real-world problems are presented and analyzed using the proposed method, and the optimal strategy is determined for each case. Taghipour et al. (2016) studied "The impact of ICT on knowledge sharing obstacles in knowledge management process (including case-study)." Jamshidi & Hatef (2016), in research entitled "identifying the reasons for contractors' claims in D-B-B contracts and evaluating them by the AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) multi-criteria decision-making models," concluded that in most projects using different delivery systems,

entities, especially contractors, may raise a claim. In addition, claims and disagreements are inevitable in Bid Design projects, especially in Design-Bid-Build (D-B-B) contracts, which are not commonly used in Iran. The focus of this study is the causes of claims raised in projects delivered by Design-Bid-Build (D-B-B) contracts.

Taghipour et al.(2015) studied "Risk analysis in the management of urban construction projects from the perspective of the employer and the contractor." Mohammad et al. (2015) studied "Assessing the effect of the FRP system on compressive and shear bending strength of concrete elements." Jalili et al. (2015) studied "Comparative study of Khaje Rashid al-Din views on Rab-e Rashidi Islamic Utopia and Kevin Lynch ideas." Rezvani et al.(2015) discussed "The design of high-rise building with ecological approach in Iran (Alborz Province)." Taghipour and Yazdi(2015) studied "Seismic analysis (non-linear static analysis (pushover) and nonlinear dynamic) on Cable-Stayed Bridge."

Table 1: Common claims in the DBB contracts (theoretical framework of the study)

Delay in result	Reference
The price of payments and invoices do not match	Shen et al. (2017)
Suspension of the work	Park et al., (2016)
Insufficient definition of work scope	Noorozma & Adnan (2015)
Orders of change in the project	Noorozma & Adnan (2015)
Unilateral termination of the contract	Arshad et al., (2019)
Stoppage of work by the contractor	Jan (2018)
Design problems	Buenaventura (2015)
Changes beyond the contract	Dastyar et al. (2018)
Disagreement in evaluations	Rastegar et al., (2019)
Ambiguity in contract	Arshad et al., (2019)
Construction violations	Calessas et al., (2020)
Harsh weather conditions and slow work	Zhou et al., (2020)
Failure to determine the responsibility of each party to the contract	Jan (2018)
Failure of the parties to the contract to respond to each other in time	Jan (2018)
The rise in the project cost over the contractual limit	Zhou et al., (2020)
The irresponsibility of some agents	Calessas et al., (2020)
Failure of the employer to provide the financial resources to the contractor on time	Arshad et al., (2019)
Lack of sufficient supervision of the employer on the project implementation process	Dastyar et al. (2018)
Unequal contractual conditions and a domineering view of the contractor	Dastyar et al. (2018)
Engineers not being familiar with the features of construction contracts	Zhou et al., (2020)
Not considering force majeure conditions in the contract	Bunaventura (2016)
Poor project management	Calessas et al., (2020)
Stopping the project for political reasons	Rastegar et al., (2019)

Change in site conditions	Dastyar et al. (2018)
Unexpected change in the price of materials	Jan (2018)
Incompetence of the contractor	Arshad et al., (2019)
Lack of quality control	Arshad et al., (2019)

Table 2: Factors effective on the claims (environment)

Claims	Reference
Contract type	Shen et al. (2017)
Parties to the contract	Park et al., (2016)
Governmental rules	Calessas et al., (2020)

3. Methodology

The research methodology is applied with a developmental approach. In terms of data collection, it is descriptive research with a design strategy. The statistical population includes the experts of the first-ranked contracting companies in Tehran with at least postgraduate education. Among 175 experts, 120 were selected based on Cochran's formula as the sample size.

Table 2: Frequency distribution of statistical sample based on demographic variables

Variable	Amounts	Abundance	Abundance percentage	Cumulative frequency percentage
Age	Below 35	20	17	17
	35-40	40	33	50
	40-45	30	25	75
	Above 45	30	25	100
	Total	120	100	
Education	Amounts	Abundance	Abundance percentage	Cumulative frequency percentage
	Master	70	58	58
	Ph.D.	50	42	100
	Total	120	100	

As the findings in Table 3 show, 20 of the respondents (17%) are under 35 years old, 33% are 35 to 40 years old, 25% are 40 to 45 years old, and 25% are 45 years old and above. Also, 70 respondents (58%) have a postgraduate degree, and 50 (42%) have a doctoral degree.

Fig 1: Frequency distribution of statistical sample members based on demographic variables

Now it is necessary to rank the factors mentioned in the questionnaire on a 5-point Likert scale to determine the importance of each one in terms of priority. Table 3 presents the 25th quartile, the 50th quartile or the median, and the 75th quartile.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of responses to questionnaires

Questions	Amount	25th	50th	75th	Questions	Amount	25th	50th	75th
Q1	12	2.12	2.94	3.47	Q15	12	2.23	3.08	3.69
Q2	12	2.1	2.92	3.41	Q16	12	2.02	2.69	3.15
Q3	12	2.09	2.89	3.36	Q17	12	2.21	3.07	3.64
Q4	12	1.91	2.4	2.86	Q18	12	1.8	2.19	2.69
Q5	12	2.2	3.15	3.8	Q19	12	2.02	2.66	3.14
Q6	12	2.26	3.11	3.75	Q20	12	1.8	2.16	2.65
Q7	12	1.86	2.3	2.8	Q21	12	2.2	3.02	3.6
Q8	12	1.83	2.2	2.74	Q22	12	2.01	2.63	3.12
Q9	12	1.8	2.15	2.6	Q23	12	2	2.6	3.08
Q10	12	2.07	2.84	3.3	Q24	12	2	2.56	3.04
Q11	12	2.05	2.8	3.28	Q25	12	2.17	3	3.53
Q12	12	2.05	2.77	3.24	Q26	12	1.98	2.51	3
Q13	12	2.03	2.71	3.2	Q27	12	1.95	2.43	2.94
Q14	12	2.04	2.75	3.2	Q28	12	2.14	2.98	3.5

Fig 2: Chart of quartiles associated with each question

Table 4: Average rank

Questions	average rank	Questions	average rank
Q1	2.77	Q15	2.88
Q2	2.76	Q16	2.66
Q3	2.74	Q17	2.86
Q4	2.4	Q18	2.26
Q5	2.96	Q19	2.62
Q6	2.93	Q20	2.2
Q7	2.33	Q21	2.83
Q8	2.32	Q22	2.58
Q9	2.16	Q23	2.55
Q10	2.73	Q24	2.5
Q11	2.72	Q25	2.8
Q12	2.7	Q26	2.48
Q13	2.67	Q27	2.45
Q14	2.69	Q28	2.78

Table 5: Ranking

Factor	Rank	Factor	Rank
Unilateral termination of the contract	1	Failure to determine the responsibility of each party to the contract	15
Stoppage of work by the contractor	2	The irresponsibility of some agents	16
The rise in the project cost over the contractual limit	3	Unequal contractual conditions and a domineering view of the contractor	17
Failure of the employer to provide the financial resources to the contractor on time	4	Poor project management	18
Not considering force majeure conditions in the contract	5	Stopping the project for political reasons	19
Unexpected change in the price of materials	6	Change in site conditions	20
Delay in result	7	Incompetence of the contractor	21
The price of payments and invoices do not match	8	Lack of quality control	22
Suspension of the work	9		23
Insufficient definition of work scope	10	Design problems	24
Ambiguity in contract	11	Changes beyond the contract	25
Construction violations	12	Lack of sufficient supervision of the employer on the project implementation process	26
Harsh weather conditions and slow work	13	Engineers not being familiar with the features of construction contracts	27
Failure of the parties to the contract to respond to each other in time	14	Disagreement in evaluations	28

Table 6: Friedman test

12	N
7.36	Chi-squared
2	df
0/029	Sig

The above table shows the Chi-squared test statistic, degrees of freedom (df), and statistical significance (Asymp. Sig.) or the p-value, all of which should be presented in the analysis results report. Therefore, it can be seen that, in general, there is a significant difference between the average ranks of the dependent and the independent variable groups ($\text{sig} < 0.05$). In other words, since the p-value is equal to 0.032, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the questions of the questionnaire in terms of importance and from the point of view of the respondents, these questions do not have the same value and importance. Next, the median value of each question can be checked, and it can be determined which one has a higher median value and is more important.

4. Conclusion

The possibility of claims cannot be eliminated in any project; however, it is possible to largely prevent them from occurring in future projects by identifying the main causes of claims and the relationship between them. Construction projects are complex, unique, and dynamic due to many influencing factors, high financial circulation, specialization and uniqueness of activities, workload, novelty and innovation, sensitivity, diverse locations, and the involvement of different people in the project. Also, on the other hand, the construction industry is always facing problems that increase the time and costs of the project, and that is a reason why the project is not completed with the intended quality. The claims and conflicts may emerge in the contracting agreements due to different reasons. Such conditions increase the probability of claims and conflicts in different stages of project implementation. Sometimes, after the claim is raised, much time is spent to settle it, and sometimes, due to the passage of time and the problems becoming obsolete, some new aspects are added to the claims, becoming more complex. As a result, more cost is imposed on the project. Since the number of claims in the construction project is increasing, determination of their causes and clearly understanding the complexity of the factors causing a claim can be the main step to preventing the claims and reducing them.

To achieve a systematic and appropriate method to resolve contractual disputes, first of all, a method should be adopted to prevent disputes as much as possible, and secondly, a mechanism should be designed so that any claims and disputes from the parties to the contract can be handled and resolved in the minimum possible time. The complexity of the contractor's claim system in construction industry projects, especially in turnkey contracts where the contractor faces more risks and has more responsibility, requires a detailed understanding of the existing claims. Particularly, in international projects, and from the middle of the project onwards, it is necessary to identify all the elements of the project to fully understand the claims that have arisen and how they relate to each of the components of the project system, to prevent the occurrence of multiple

claims. Also, with the management of the claims, the claims arisen should be dealt with in more detail. To do so, the system dynamics method must be necessarily used. Claims are also becoming one of the inseparable parts of contracts, and by identifying these claims, their occurrence in the project can be prevented to a large extent. Claims and subsequent disputes have become the inherent characteristics of the construction and production industry, which many project beneficiaries consider to be one of the most destructive events in this industry. Although the possibility of these claims cannot be eliminated in any project, identifying the factors that cause it can be prevented to a large extent. Based on the findings presented in the current research, it was determined that the identified factors could lead to claim management because it has been objectively shown in the research of Shen et al. (2017) that the lack of harmony between the payments and invoices can lead to an increase in claims in DBB contracts. Also, it has been shown in the research by Park et al. (2016) that the suspension of work can lead to increased claims in DBB contracts. Noorozma and Adnan (2015) showed that an insufficient definition of the scope of work and change orders in the project could lead to increased claims in DBB contracts. In the research by Arshad et al. (2019), it has been shown that the unilateral termination of the contract can lead to an increase in claims in DBB contracts. Jan's research (2018) indicated that the stoppage of work by the contractor and an unexpected change in the price of materials could also lead to an increase in claims in DBB contracts. In the research by Bonaventura (2015), it has been concluded that design problems and not considering the force majeure conditions in the contract can lead to increased claims in DBB contracts.

Moreover, Dastiyar et al. (2018) showed that changes beyond the contract, the employer's lack of sufficient monitoring of the project implementation process and unequal contractual conditions, an imperious view of the contractor, and changes in the site conditions could lead to an increase in claims in DBB contracts. It has been shown in the research by Rastegar et al. (2019) that disagreements in the evaluation and stopping the project due to political reasons can also lead to an increase in claims in DBB contracts. Arshad et al.'s research (2019) showed that ambiguity in the contract and failure to provide timely financial resources from the employer to the contractor could increase claims in DBB contracts. In the research by Calessas et al. (2020), it has been shown that violations in construction and irresponsibility of some agents, as well as poor project management, can lead to increased claims in DBB contracts. Also, Zhou et al. (2020) showed that harsh atmospheric conditions and slowness of the work, as well as the increase in the project cost beyond the contractual limit and the lack of familiarity of engineers with the characteristics of construction contracts, can lead to an increase in claims in DBB contracts. It has been shown in the research of Jan (2018) that the lack of clear determination of the responsibility of each of the parties to the contract and the failure of the parties to the contract to respond to each other in time can lead to an increase in claims in DBB contracts.

Finally, the following suggestions are provided:

- Employing experts in the field of claims and using them in an institution called the 'Claims Management Office' in the project
- Enactment of standard rules by the Construction Engineering Organization to consider solutions and notes for all the claims mentioned in the current research

- Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) for factors affecting the development of claims in DBB contracts
- Culturalization of honesty, responsibility, and trustworthiness in cultural organizations
- Preparation of authentic moral training clips
- Research and Development (R&D) about cultural changes in the organization
- Determining the feasibility of cultural policies under the supervision of cultural managers
- Using smart policies with the participation of cultural managers
- Using attractive cultural policies

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